

ICT and Emotional Intelligence Competencies of Business Studies Teachers in Rivers State: A Critical Assessment for Effective Curriculum Delivery

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Abstract

The study assessed the ICT and Emotional Intelligence Competencies of Teachers required for Implementation of Business Studies Curriculum in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State. Two research questions and hypotheses guided the study. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population consisted of 76 Business Subjects' Teachers in the three Senatorial Districts in Rivers State. A validated 4-point scale questionnaire containing 11 items were used for data collection. Their responses were collated and analyzed using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient (PPMCC) and a reliability coefficient of 0.8664 was obtained. Mean and Standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while ANOVA was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings of the study revealed that all the respondents agreed on all items of ICT and Emotional Intelligence Competencies required for the Implementation of Business Studies Curriculum in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State. There was no significant difference in the mean responses of Teachers in Rivers East, Rivers West and Rivers South-East Senatorial Districts in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State. It was recommended that the State Ministries of Education should establish ICT centers for Teachers in all Public Secondary Schools to enable Teachers have access to the needed ICT tools for instilling these skills in their students; and Emotional intelligence Experts such as Psychologists and Guidance and Counselling Therapists should be contracted by Public Secondary School Authorities to periodically organize Conferences, workshops, and symposia with Business subjects' teachers. This will afford them the opportunity to improve their emotional competence that will enable them manage students properly.

Keywords: ICT Competencies; Emotional Intelligence Competencies; Business Studies Curriculum.

Introduction

The integration of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) and emotional intelligence in secondary school education has been widely acknowledged as a crucial factor in enhancing teaching and learning processes, improving student outcomes, and increasing student engagement (Ololube, 2013; UNESCO, 2018). The benefits of ICTs in education are well-documented, including improved access to information, enhanced collaboration, and more efficient management and monitoring within schools.

Similarly, emotional intelligence is essential for effective teaching, as it enables teachers to manage their emotions, empathize with students, and create a positive learning environment (Mortiboy, 2013). In the context of business studies education, the acquisition of ICT skills and

emotional intelligence competencies is critical for teachers to create interactive and student-centered learning environments (Oyerinde, Onnoh, & Adebanyo, 2020).

The implementation of the Business Studies curriculum in Nigerian secondary schools is a critical aspect of education that requires careful planning and execution. Business Studies is a vital subject that equips students with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary for success in the business world (NERDC, 2017). Effective implementation of the Business Studies curriculum requires teachers who are not only knowledgeable in the subject matter but also possess the necessary ICT skills and emotional intelligence competencies.

Despite the importance of ICT and emotional intelligence in business studies education, there is a need to assess the competencies of teachers in these areas (Ibrahim, 2017). This is particularly relevant in the Nigerian context, where there is a growing recognition of the need to integrate ICTs and emotional intelligence into teacher education programs (Federal Ministry of Education, 2019). This study aims to investigate the ICT and emotional intelligence competencies required by Business Studies teachers in Rivers State, Nigeria, in order to effectively implement the Business Studies curriculum. The study will provide insights into the current state of ICT infrastructure and teacher training programs in Nigerian schools, as well as the emotional intelligence competencies of Business Studies teachers.

Statement of Problem

Despite the importance of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) and emotional intelligence in enhancing teaching and learning processes, there is a growing concern that Business Studies teachers in Rivers State, Nigeria, may lack the necessary ICT skills and emotional intelligence competencies to effectively implement the Business Studies curriculum. This study seeks to investigate the ICT and emotional intelligence competencies required by Business Studies teachers in Rivers State, Nigeria, in order to effectively implement the Business Studies curriculum.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to assess Professional Requirements of Teachers for Implementation of Business Studies Curriculum in Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the Information and Communication Technology competencies required for the implementation of business subject curriculum.
2. Determine the emotional intelligence competencies required for the implementation of the business studies curriculum.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What information and communication technology competencies are required for the implementation of business studies curriculum?
2. What emotional intelligence competencies are required for the implementation of the business studies curriculum?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study and were tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of teachers in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers West Senatorial District and Rivers South East Senatorial District on the Information and Communication Technology competencies required by Teachers for the implementation of business studies curriculum.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of teachers in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers West Senatorial District and Rivers South East Senatorial District on the emotional intelligence competencies required by Teachers for the implementation of business subject curriculum.

Method

This study aimed to investigate the professional requirements of teachers necessary for the effective implementation of the Business Studies curriculum in public secondary schools in Rivers State. To achieve this objective, a descriptive survey design was adopted. This design was chosen to enable the researcher to collect data from study population of teachers using a questionnaire, thereby providing a comprehensive understanding of the professional requirements necessary for effective curriculum implementation. The population of the study comprised all Business Studies teachers in public secondary schools in Rivers East, Rivers West, and Rivers South East Senatorial Districts. A total of 76 teachers were randomly selected from the population and participated in the study. A structured questionnaire, titled "Business Studies Teachers' Professional Requirements Questionnaire (BSTPRQ)," was developed to collect data from the respondents. The BSTPRQ consisted of 11 items and was rated on a 4-point scale: Strongly Agree (SA) = 4 points, Agree (A) = 3 points, Disagree (D) = 2 points, and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 point.

The BSTPRQ was subjected to face and content validation by two experts from the Departments of Business Education and Measurement and Evaluation in Rivers State University. The reliability of the instrument was determined using the test-retest method, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.8664. The questionnaire was administered to the respondents by the researcher and two research assistants. The retrieved questionnaires were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. The mean ratings were interpreted using the following boundary limits: Strongly Agree (3.50 – 4.00), Agree (2.50 – 3.49), Disagree (1.50 – 2.49), and Strongly Disagree (0.50 – 1.49). The hypotheses were tested using One-way ANOVA, with the hypotheses accepted when the F-cal was less than the table value and rejected when the F-critical was greater than the F-cal value.

Results

Research Question 1: What information and communication technology competencies are required for the implementation of business studies curriculum?

Table 1: Mean Ratings on the Information and Communication Technology Competencies required by Business Studies Teachers for the Implementation of Business Subjects Curriculum

S/No	Questionnaire Items	Senatorial Districts								
		Rivers East (N=43)			Rivers West (N=16)			Rivers South East (N = 17)		
		Mean	St.D	Rmk	Mean	St.D	Rmk	Mean	St.D	Rmk
1.	The ability to use the internet for teaching selected topics can enable teachers to implement the curriculum needs of business subjects	3.16	0.68	A	2.93	0.80	A	3.12	0.76	A
2.	The ability to use power point for teaching presentations can enable teachers to implement the curriculum needs of business subjects	3.35	0.64	A	3.19	0.81	A	3.12	0.76	A
3.	The ability to use data base in entering figures when teaching the calculation aspects of business subjects can enable you to implement the curriculum needs of business subjects	3.49	0.50	A	3.50	0.50	SA	3.47	0.61	A
4.	The ability to analyze data using excel package can enable teachers to implement the curriculum needs of business subjects	3.44	0.66	A	3.31	0.85	A	3.41	0.60	A
5.	The ability to store and retrieve data in a suitable storage can enable teachers to implement the curriculum needs of business subjects	3.47	0.50	A	3.38	0.60	A	3.24	0.70	A
6.	The ability to make graphic presentations using PowerPoint during lessons can enable teachers to implement the curriculum needs of business subjects	3.28	0.68	A	3.13	0.86	A	3.18	0.78	A
Grand Mean/St.D		3.37	0.61	A	3.24	0.74	A	3.26	0.70	A

Table 1 shows that the respondents agreed on all items of information and communication technology competencies needed by Business Studies Teachers for the Implementation of Business Subjects Curriculum (mean scores > 2.5) from all the senatorial districts. The grand mean of 3.37, 3.24 and 3.26.84 from Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers West Senatorial District and Rivers South East Senatorial District respectively is an indication that business studies teachers in these Senatorial Districts agreed that information and communication technology competencies are required by Business Studies Teachers in the Implementation of Business Studies Curriculum in Rivers State. Also, results revealed that the grand standard deviation (SD) of the items ranged from 0.61 to 0.74, indicating that the respondents were not too far from one another in their responses.

Research Question 2: What emotional intelligence competencies are required for the implementation of the business studies curriculum?

Table 2: Mean Ratings on the Emotional Intelligence Competencies needed by Business Studies Teachers for the Implementation of Business Subjects Curriculum

S/No	Questionnaire Items	Senatorial Districts								
		Rivers East (N=43)			Rivers West (N=16)			Rivers South East (N = 17)		
		Mean	St.D	Rmk	Mean	St.D	Rmk	Mean	St.D	Rmk
7.	The ability to manage conflicts among students during class lessons can enable teachers to implement the curriculum needs of business subjects	2.65	0.90	A	2.94	1.03	SA	3.12	0.83	A
8.	Taking note of students' countenance and giving adequate attention during class lessons can enable you to implement the curriculum needs of business subjects	3.35	0.68	A	3.25	0.83	A	3.24	0.81	A
9.	The ability to recognize and respond to students' questions promptly can enable you to implement the curriculum needs of business subjects	3.12	0.95	A	3.00	0.87	A	2.71	0.85	A
10.	Ability to relate better with students can enable you to implement the curriculum needs of business subjects	3.37	0.68	A	3.13	0.78	A	3.29	0.57	A
11.	Possessing inner self-control can enable you to implement the	3.40	0.53	A	3.31	0.58	A	3.24	0.55	A

Table 4:
Summary of Analysis of Variance for Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers West Senatorial District, Rivers South East Senatorial District on the Emotional Competencies needed by Teachers for the implementation of Business Studies Curriculum

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	Degree of Freedom	Mean Square	F-cal.	F-tab.	Level of Sig.	Dec.
Between Groups	6.25	2	3.13				
Within Groups	113.28	73	1.55	2.02	4.92	0.05	NS
Total	119.53	75					

Table 4 showed the summary of ANOVA result on the difference in the mean responses of Business Subjects Teachers in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers West Senatorial District, Rivers South East Senatorial District on the emotional intelligence competencies required for the implementation of Business Studies Curriculum. The table also showed that the calculated F value is $= 2.02$. $< F_{crit. (0.05, 2, 73)} = 4.92$. The null hypothesis is accepted. It is therefore concluded that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of teachers in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers West Senatorial District and Rivers South East Senatorial District on the emotional intelligence competencies required by Teachers for the implementation of business studies curriculum.

Discussion of Findings

The data collected in this study were thoroughly analyzed, and the results were presented and discussed in relation to the research questions and hypotheses that guided the investigation. The findings of the study on research question 1 showed the following Information and Communication Technology competencies required by Teachers for the implementation of business studies curriculum: The ability to use the internet for teaching selected topics can enable teachers to implement the curriculum needs of business subjects; the ability to use power point for teaching presentations can enable teachers to implement the curriculum needs of business subjects; the ability to use data base in entering figures when teaching the calculation aspects of business subjects can enable you to implement the curriculum needs of business subjects; the ability to analyze data using excel package can enable teachers to implement the curriculum needs of business subjects; the ability to store and retrieve data in a suitable storage can enable teachers to implement the curriculum needs of business subjects and the ability to make graphic presentations

using PowerPoint during lessons can enable teachers to implement the curriculum needs of business subjects.

In agreement with the above facts, Akudolu and Ololube (2013) noted that Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is indispensable competency area that is required for effective teaching of business subjects in secondary schools. With the evolving technologies, the teaching profession is advancing from an emphasis on teacher-centered, lecture-based instruction to student-centered and interactive learning environments.

In a similar note, Oyerinde, Onnoh and Adebayo (2020) submitted that, for business subject teachers to contribute absolutely to the development of their students, they must acquire pertinent Information and Communication Technology competencies which include but not limited to: the ability to use the internet for teaching selected topics, the ability to make use of power point for instruction or presentations, the ability to use data base in entering figures, anywhere and anyplace. It must be noted that lack of relevant Information and Communication Technology competencies or skills by teacher of any category could hamper the realization of educational goals in the contemporary society. Acquisition of relevant ICT skills by business subject teachers would therefore create an enabling environment for them to open Microsoft word application, network computer to exchange files, write educational programmes, select and evaluate subject specific education software, develop computer assisted software, develop software to teach a subject exhaustively and effectively, develop software to evaluate instruction among others.

Information and Communication Technology competencies include voice, body language and words such as speaking, singing and sometimes tone of voice, sign language, touch, eye contact, or the use of writing. They include communication skills in intra personal and interpersonal processing, listening, observing, speaking, questioning, analyzing, and evaluating which are translated into technology know-how.

Hypotheses 1 stated that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of teachers in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers West Senatorial District and Rivers South East Senatorial District on the Information and Communication Technology competencies required for the implementation of business studies curriculum. In a similar vein, Selvi (2013) opined that Information and Communication Technologies competencies are involve using tools and technical equipment for the reaching, distributing and transferring the knowledge. They include any technology that aids to produce, store, manipulate, communicate, and/or disseminate information. ICT competencies are concerned with the use of technology in managing and processing the information include all technologies for the manipulation and communication of information Teachers should also have competencies in using oral, body and professional language in their fields.

Because Communication is like lifeblood, it is very important to improve the communication in the learning and teaching process (Danielson, 2015). That is to say that Information and Communication Technologies competencies are essential for the implementation of Business subjects' curriculum. If communication is interrupted or ineffectual, there will certainly be a blockage in the circulation which will eventually affect curriculum implementation.

Results from research question 2 revealed the following emotional competencies: The ability to manage conflicts among students during class lessons can enable teachers to implement the curriculum needs of business subjects; taking note of students' countenance and giving adequate attention during class lessons can enable you to implement the curriculum needs of business

subjects; the ability to recognize and respond to students' questions promptly can enable you to implement the curriculum needs of business subjects; ability to relate better with students can enable you to implement the curriculum needs of business subjects and possessing inner self-control can enable you to implement the curriculum needs of business subjects.

In support of the above idea, Mortiboys (2013) noted that emotional intelligence of a business subject teacher is indispensable. A teacher should be able to manage their positive and negative emotions of students and should be able to understand and manage conflicts or the effect of those emotion on others students. Basically, an effective teacher should have adequate self-knowledge or awareness of his/her feelings, values and attitudes as a teacher, awareness of his/her behavior and how others view them. Teachers with high Emotional Intelligence competencies are positive, adaptable, collaborative, self-confident, convincing, open, approachable and enthusiastic. They have better impulse and self-control. Hence, an effective teacher has effective self-control, they are more controlled and mature. Teachers' persistence aids in fostering effective teaching and learning.

Hypotheses 2 stated that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of teachers in Rivers East Senatorial District, Rivers West Senatorial District and Rivers South East Senatorial District on the emotional intelligence competencies required for the implementation of business studies curriculum.

On a similar note, Selvi, (2013) maintained that Emotional Competencies are composed of teachers' values, morals, beliefs, attitudes, anxieties, motivation, and empathy among others. They are related to the implementation of psychological consultation and curriculum of business subject curriculum in schools. Teachers' emotional competencies can help students to learn, and students' willingness to learn can be increased if teachers know how to improve the emotional dimension of students' learning. Hence, it is obvious that Emotional competencies help teachers become effective teachers while monitoring the students' learning as Learning involves emotional supports that create positive feeling for learning-teaching process.

Together with instructional methods in class, the way teachers and students connect and interact with each other is a decisive factor to determine student's academic attainment and social development (Hamre & Pianta, 2013). Teachers' wellbeing and their skills dealing with the diverse needs to students could impact strongly on teacher-student relationship. Firstly, it is a matter of fact that teachers' wellbeing has direct link to students' wellbeing. In an empirical research, Oberle and Schonert-Reichl (2016) remark that cortisol levels in the morning in students can be linked to teacher burnout. The researchers also comment that students will typically perceive teachers' negative emotions and its manifestation, and the negative emotions are contagious which could pose the harm on teacher-student healthy relationship (Schonert-Reichl, 2017).

In contrast, teachers with high Emotional Competence are those who recognize an individual student's emotions, understand the intellectual appraisals behind that. These teachers make sense for their students' emotionally motivated reasons and the sequence behaviors (Jennings & Greenberg, 2015; Roffey, 2016). When teachers are able to understand their students' emotional makeup, expression and the respective appraisals, they have more feelings of their meaningful roles by their students' sides, likely to get closer to students' circumstances, understand them more and find the best way to support students overcoming their daily difficulties, either physical and emotional ones. As such, teachers become the reliable and effectively supportive sources for students. As a result, both teachers' and students' wellbeing are ensured and it warrants a significantly healthy relationship of them (Roffey, 2016, p. 1).

Conclusion

The findings of this study revealed that Information and Communication Technology (ICT) competences and Emotional Intelligence (EI) competences are essential for Business Studies teachers to effectively implement the Business Studies curriculum. This suggests that the practice of competency improvement needs of teachers, particularly in the areas of ICT and EI, is crucial for the successful implementation of the Business Studies curriculum.

The study's results also showed that Business Studies teachers in public secondary schools across Rivers East, Rivers West, and Rivers South East Senatorial Districts share similar views on the importance of ICT and EI competences for effective curriculum implementation. This consensus underscores the need for teacher professional training programmes to prioritize the development of these critical competences.

In conclusion, this study provides empirical evidence supporting the importance of ICT and EI competences for Business Studies teachers. The findings have implications for teacher education and professional development programmes, highlighting the need to integrate ICT and EI training to enhance teacher effectiveness and student learning outcomes.

Recommendations

1. The State Ministries of Education should establish ICT centres for Teachers in all Public Secondary Schools to enable Teachers have access to the needed ICT tools for instilling these skills in their students.
2. Emotional intelligence Experts such as Psychologists and Guidance and Counselling Therapists should be contracted by Public Secondary School Authorities to periodically organize Conferences, workshops, and symposia with Business subjects' teachers. This will afford them the opportunity to improve their emotional competence that will enable them manage students properly

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